

Longitudinal Shear Modulus of Unidirectional Composites

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ABSTRACT

Effective longitudinal shear modulus of unidirectional composites with random array packing of fibers is predicted by establishing a random model. It is shown that if the degree of the randomness increases, the shear modulus increases remarkably. Comparison of the theoretical prediction with experimental data available for glass-epoxy, graphite-epoxy and boron-epoxy composites reveals that this random model is physically more realistic than others proposed in the literature for the actual unidirectional composites.

INTRODUCTION

The elastic modulus of unidirectional fiber-reinforced composites associated with a shear loading in the direction of the fibers is one of the fundamental material properties. It has been recognized that experimental data for the longitudinal shear modulus of glass-epoxy composites is higher than theoretical predictions based on a periodic hexagonal array of fibers, and is equal to or higher than those based on a square array of fibers although the hexagonal array is considered to be more representative of actual material geometry than the square array. This result may be attributed to the fact that the fibers in actual unidirectional composites are randomly distributed.

Hashin[1] obtained upper and lower bounds of the longitudinal shear modulus for actual unidirectional composites by a variational method, and Nomura and Chou [2] provided tighter bounds. Chou, Nomura and Taya[3] predicted the shear modulus by a self-consistent approach proposed by Hill[4] with the results falling within Nomura and Chou's bounds. Tsai[5] used a procedure to predict the shear modulus of actual composites by linearly combining Hashin's upper and lower bounds through the so-called contiguity factor which is a measure of the randomness of fiber packing.

In the present paper, the longitudinal shear modulus of actual unidirectional composites is predicted by establishing a random model which was proposed for estimation of the transverse moisture diffusivity of composites by Kondo and Taki [6,7]. The theoretical prediction is compared with experimental data available in the literature for glass-epoxy, graphite-epoxy and boron-epoxy composites.

PREDICTION OF EFFECTIVE LONGITUDINAL SHEAR MODULUS

Theory

A unidirectional fiber-reinforced composite material is referred to cartesian coordinates x , y and z where x and y are in the transverse plane while z is in the fiber direction as shown in Fig.1. If the fibers and matrix are assumed to be transversely isotropic for the longitudinal shear loading, the shear stresses τ and the shear strains γ are connected by the relations

$$\begin{aligned} \tau_{m,xz} &= G_m \gamma_{m,xz} & \tau_{m,yz} &= G_m \gamma_{m,yz} \\ \tau_{f,xz} &= G_f \gamma_{f,xz} & \tau_{f,yz} &= G_f \gamma_{f,yz} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where G is the longitudinal shear modulus and the subscripts m and f refer to the matrix and fiber, respectively. If the fibers are all identical and arranged symmetrically with respect to the rotation about the z axis by $\pi/3$ or $\pi/2$, or if the fibers are randomly dispersed, the composite is transversely isotropic for the longitudinal shear loading. Then, the overall longitudinal shear modulus G_{LT} is defined by

$$\langle \tau_{xz} \rangle = G_{LT} \langle \gamma_{xz} \rangle \quad \langle \tau_{yz} \rangle = G_{LT} \langle \gamma_{yz} \rangle \quad (2)$$

where $\langle \quad \rangle$ denotes the volume average.

The composite is assumed to be subjected to the boundary displacements

$$u(s) = 0 \quad v(s) = 0 \quad w(s) = y \quad (3)$$

where u , v and w are the displacements in the x , y and z directions, respectively. Then, the displacement field is given by

$$u = 0 \quad v = 0 \quad w = \bar{w}(x,y) \quad (4)$$

which yields the nonvanishing strain components as

$$\gamma_{xz} = \frac{\partial \bar{w}}{\partial x} \quad \gamma_{yz} = \frac{\partial \bar{w}}{\partial y} \quad (5)$$

And the divergence theorem gives

$$\langle \gamma_{xz} \rangle = 0 \quad \langle \gamma_{yz} \rangle = 1 \quad (6)$$

It follows from Eqs.(1) and (5) that

$$\begin{aligned} \tau_{m,xz} &= G_m \frac{\partial \bar{w}_m}{\partial x} & \tau_{m,yz} &= G_m \frac{\partial \bar{w}_m}{\partial y} \\ \tau_{f,xz} &= G_f \frac{\partial \bar{w}_f}{\partial x} & \tau_{f,yz} &= G_f \frac{\partial \bar{w}_f}{\partial y} \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

The equilibrium equation in the z direction gives

$$\frac{\partial^2 \bar{w}_m}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \bar{w}_m}{\partial y^2} = 0 \quad \frac{\partial^2 \bar{w}_f}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \bar{w}_f}{\partial y^2} = 0 \quad (8)$$

where the continuity conditions at the interface between the fiber and the matrix are

$$\bar{w}_m = \bar{w}_f \quad G_m \frac{\partial \bar{w}_m}{\partial n} = G_f \frac{\partial \bar{w}_f}{\partial n} \quad (9)$$

where n is a coordinate normal to the interface. From Eqs.(7), the volume average of the shear stress τ_{yz} is given by

$$\langle \tau_{yz} \rangle = \langle G_f \frac{\partial \bar{w}}{\partial y} \rangle \quad (10)$$

Therefore, substitution of Eqs.(6) and (10) into Eq.(2) yields the effective longitudinal shear modulus as

$$\langle G_{LT} \rangle = \langle G_0 \frac{\partial \bar{w}}{\partial y} \rangle \quad (11)$$

Method of Analysis

Firstly, the effective shear modulus is predicted for a regular array of fibers. It is assumed that the fibers are of identical circular cross section and form a hexagonal or square array in the transverse plane as shown in Fig.2. Because of the symmetry of array, it is sufficient to consider only a typical repeating unit of the composite as represented in Fig.3. The shear loading problem governed by Eqs.(8) and (9) is solved by the finite element method utilizing the eight-node isoparametric quadrilateral elements. The prescribed boundary displacements are

$$\bar{w}_m = \bar{w}_f = 0 \quad \text{at } y = 0, \quad \bar{w}_m = \bar{w}_f = 1 \quad \text{at } y = 1 \quad (12)$$

and the symmetry conditions require that

$$\frac{\partial \bar{w}_m}{\partial x} = \frac{\partial \bar{w}_f}{\partial y} = 0 \quad \text{at } x = 0 \text{ and } \sqrt{3} \quad (13)$$

It follows from Eq.(11) that the effective longitudinal shear modulus is determined by

$$G_{LT} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} \int_0^1 \int_0^{\sqrt{3}} G_0 \frac{\partial \bar{w}}{\partial y} dx dy \quad (14)$$

Next, the effective shear modulus for a random array of fibers is predicted by establishing a random model which has a square array of square cylinders of matrix embedded in the hexagonal packing composite as shown in Fig.4. The ratio of the side length of the square cross section of cylinder to the distance between the centers of the adjacent square cross sections is β . Therefore the volume fraction of the pure matrix cylinders is β^2 . Because of the geometrical symmetry, it is sufficient to consider a repeating unit as depicted in Fig.5. The displacement field $\bar{w}(x,y)$ is determined by the finite element method utilizing the eight-node isoparametric quadrilateral elements with the effective shear modulus of the hexagonal array composite obtained beforehand.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The theoretical predictions of the effective longitudinal shear modulus D_{LT} for the hexagonal and square array composites are shown in Figs.6 and 7 as a function of the fiber volume fraction V_f in the cases of glass-epoxy ($G_f/G_m = 20$) and boron-epoxy ($G_f/G_m = 120$) systems. It can be seen that the shear modulus for the hexagonal array is lower than that for the square array. The difference is large at higher values of V_f while it is small at lower values of V_f . Also indicated in Figs.6 and 7 are experimental data taken from the literature [5, 8, 11-14, 17]. Most experimental results are higher than the theoretical predictions based on the regular packing of fibers. Similar observations can be made for the graphite-epoxy composites [5, 8, 13-14].

The theoretical predictions of the shear modulus based on the random model are shown in Figs.8 and 9 as a function of the fiber volume fraction V_f for several values of β in the cases of glass-epoxy and boron-epoxy composites, respectively. As can be seen, if β increases, that is, if the degree of the randomness increases, the longitudinal shear modulus increases remarkably. The influence of β on the shear modulus is small at lower values of V_f while it is large at higher values of V_f . However, much higher values of V_f can be attained only by composites with low degree of randomness due to the geometrical

restriction. Also presented in Figs.8 and 9 are experimental data available in the literature [5, 8, 11-14, 17]. The experimental data for glass-epoxy composites are scattered between the theoretical curves of $\beta^2 = 0.1$ and $\beta^2 = 0.4$ while the data for boron-epoxy composites are in good agreement with the curve of $\beta^2 = 0.1$. These results are attributed to the fact that a special effort to obtain a regular packing geometry is not made for glass-epoxy composites while it is done for boron-epoxy composites.

Comparisons of the present theoretical predictions with the upper and lower bounds [1, 2] for actual composites are shown in Figs.10 and 11 in the cases of glass-epoxy and boron-epoxy composites. It should be noted that all the present theoretical predictions are inside Hashin's bounds[1], but are not inside Nomura and Chou's improved bounds [2].

Comparison of the theoretical predictions available in the literature [1-3, 18] for the longitudinal shear modulus of actual composites with experimental data [5, 8, 11-14] are shown in Fig.12 in the case of glass-epoxy system. It can be seen that while most experimental results fall between the Voigt and Reuss bounds[18] and the tighter Hashin bounds[1], some data fall outside Nomura and Chou's bounds[2]. Therefore, the self-consistent prediction[3] which falls between the Nomura and Chou bounds gives poor agreement with the experimental data. Tsai's prediction[5] with the contiguity factor $C = 0.2$ is compared with the experimental data [5, 8, 11-14] in Fig.13 for glass-epoxy composites. Also presented are Hashin's upper and lower bounds which correspond to $C = 1.0$ and $C = 0.0$, respectively. As can be seen, Tsai's prediction agrees very well with the experimental data. However, It was found that the procedure proposed by Tsai is not applicable for the prediction of the transverse moisture diffusivity [7].

Adams and Tsai[19] predicted the transverse stiffness of actual composites by using realistic random models with the results which are higher than the predictions based on the regular array of fibers. And it was found that the scattering of the shear modulus of random models is great at intermediate values of the fiber volume fraction while it is small at higher and lower values of the fiber volume fraction. Similar observation can be made on the present theoretical predictions of the longitudinal shear modulus. It should be noted that the present model is much simpler than the random models used by Adams and Tsai.

CONCLUSIONS

It has been found that the theoretical predictions of the longitudinal shear modulus based on the regular fiber packing gives poor agreement with the experimental data. Using a random model which was successfully utilized for the prediction of transverse moisture diffusivity of actual composites by Kondo and Taki[7], the shear modulus has been predicted in terms of the degree of fiber packing randomness. It has been shown that the degree of randomness β increases, the shear modulus increases remarkably. The experimental data for glass-epoxy composites are scattered between the theoretical curves with $\beta^2 = 0.1$ and $\beta^2 = 0.4$ while the data for boron-epoxy composites are in good agreement with the theoretical curve with $\beta^2 = 0.1$. This observation shows that the fiber packing randomness of the boron-epoxy composites is less than that of the glass-epoxy composites due to the effort made to give a regular array fiber packing in the manufacturing process. Comparison of the present theoretical prediction and others available in the literature with the experimental data has revealed that the present random model seems to be physically most representative of actual composites.

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Fig.1 Coordinate system for unidirectional composite.

Fig. 2 Transverse plane of hexagonal array composite.

Fig. 3 Finite element idealization of typical repeating unit of hexagonal array composite.

Fig. 4 Transverse plane of random model.

Fig. 5 Finite element idealization of typical repeating unit of random model.

Fig.6 Theoretical predictions of longitudinal shear modulus for glass-epoxy composites based on regular array models and experimental data.

Fig.7 Theoretical predictions of longitudinal shear modulus for boron-epoxy composites based on regular array models and experimental data.

Fig.8 Theoretical predictions of longitudinal shear modulus for glass-epoxy composites based on random model and experimental data.

Fig.9 Theoretical predictions of longitudinal shear modulus for boron-epoxy composites based on random model and experimental data.

Fig.10 Comparison of present results based on random model with Hashin's and improved Nomura & Chou's bounds for glass-epoxy composites.

Fig.11 Comparison of present results based on random model with Hashin's and improved Nomura & Chou's bounds for boron-epoxy composites.

Fig.12 Comparison of theoretical predictions available in the literature with experimental data for glass-epoxy composites.

Fig.13 Comparison of Tsai's prediction with contiguity factor $C = 0.2$ with the experimental data for glass-epoxy composites.